

Extractive Photometric Determination of Osmium(VI) with N-(4-Methoxy-Phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide (R-I) and N-(4-Methyl-Phenyl)- α -Thiopicolinamide (R-II) Reagents

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Two newly synthesized reagents for liquid-liquid extraction and spectrophotometric determination of osmium are reported. The brown complexes have absorption maxima at 440 nm (R-I) and 430 nm (R-II). The systems obey Beer's law from 1-20 ppm (R-I) and 1-18 ppm (R-II) and have optimum ranges of 3-16 ppm (R-I) and 4.5-17 ppm (R-II).

The molar absorptivity values and Sandell's sensitivities are 8.3×10^3 , 6.5×10^3 l. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 0.023, 0.029 μ g Os⁶⁺ cm⁻² respectively for the two reagents. 100 fold excess of Ir⁴⁺, Ru³⁺, Rh³⁺, Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺, Cr³⁺ and many other diverse ions do not interfere. The stability constants (log K) are found to be 4.71, 4.62 with R-I and 4.52, 4.0 with R-II by photometric methods at 25 $\pm$ 1°.

OSMIUM forms intensely coloured complexes with reagents containing mercapto and thiocarbonyl groups, which are suitable for spectrophotometric determination. Thiourea^{1,2} is an important reagent for determination of osmium at ppm level but the method is not free from interferences of associated platinum metals. Several substituted thioureas³ have also been reportedly used. Further, osmium forms sensitive colour reactions⁴ with sulphonic acids, thiooxamides and thiocarbazides. 1,4,6,8-Naphthylamino trisulphonic acid was reported by Yoe and coworker as a sensitive reagent for osmium but the method is not selective. Anthranilic acid⁵ and bismuthiol(II)⁶ were reported as less selective reagents for osmium. The other sulphur bearing reagents are thiobenzhydrazide⁷, phthalimide dithiosemicarbazone⁸, α -thiosemicarbazido isobutyronitrile⁹, which give sensitive colour reactions with osmium.

Two important new thiol reagents for osmium which are found to be sensitive and selective in their colour reactions are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Hilger Uvispek and Spektromom 204 spectrophotometers, with 1 cm quartz or glass cells were used for measurement of absorbance.

Standard osmium solution: 0.1 g osmium tetroxide (Johnson Matthey) dissolved in 0.2 M sodium hydroxide and standardized iodimetrically was used. Os⁶⁺ was obtained in 1 : 2 water-ethanol medium.

Preparation of reagents: The reagents were prepared following Porter's method¹⁰. The reagent, R-I, was prepared by refluxing *p*-anisidine (2 moles), α -picoline (1 mole) and sulphur powder (1.5 mole).

The thio-compound was isolated by repeated extraction of the oily mass with petroleum ether (40-60). The ether fraction was evaporated and the yellow solid was recrystallized twice from absolute ethanol. The yield was 20% based on α -picoline, m.p. 95° (recrystallized).

The reagent, R-II, was similarly prepared by refluxing *p*-toluidine (2 moles), α -picoline (1 mole) and sulphur powder (1.5 mole). The m.p. of the product recrystallized from absolute alcohol was 97°. The chemical analysis of the reagents is reported in Table 1.

TABLE I

Reagent	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	S
I	63.68	4.56	11.60	13.20
	(63.93)	(4.92)	(11.48)	(13.11)
II	68.18	4.71	11.96	14.20
	(68.42)	(5.26)	(12.28)	(14.04)

Freshly prepared solutions of 0.1% R-I and 0.2% R-II in ethanol were used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Recommended procedure: Aliquots of osmium solution (100 μ g) are taken into separatory funnels and acidified with HCl to 0.5 M for reagent R-I and 1.5 M for R-II. 5 ml of 0.1% R-I or 4 ml of 0.2% R-II in ethanol solutions are added into the respective funnels, followed by water to make the volume 15 ml. Solutions are shaken for 5 min with 15 ml of chloroform in each case. The two layers are then allowed to separate. The chloroform solution is collected over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The aqueous phases are again shaken with 5 ml portions

of chloroform. The chloroform extracts are combined with the previous lots. The dried chloroform layer is transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and volume is made up with chloroform. The absorbances of the complexes are measured against reagent blank at 440 nm (R-I) and 430 nm (R-II).

Results and Discussion

Spectral characteristics : The absorbance of the 4 ppm osmium complexes as well as of 0.1% R-I and 0.2% R-II were measured from 400 to 540 nm. As the reagents absorb strongly, all other measurements were done against reagent blank. The complexes have absorption maxima at 440 nm and 430 nm with R-I and R-II (Fig. 1), respectively.

Fig. 1. Spectral curves of Os-thiol complexes against reagent blank and solvent blank.
1. R-I, 2. Os-complex + R-I, 3. Os-complex against R-I, 4. R-II, 5. Os-complex + R-II, 6. Os-complex against R-II.

The optimum acidity ranges for full complex formations were found to be 0.3-0.8 M HCl with R-I and 1.0-1.6 M HCl with R-II, and the optimum reagent concentrations were 1.0 to 8.0 ml of 0.1% R-I and 3.0 to 6.0 ml of 0.2% R-II. Both these complexes are stable for more than 15 hr at room temperature.

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error : The complexes obey Beer's law from 1-20 ppm (R-I) and 1-18 ppm (R-II). The optimum ranges from Ringbom's plot (Fig. 2) are 3-16 ppm (R-I) and 4.5-17 ppm (R-II). The percent relative photometric error for the systems are 2.71 (R-I) and 2.70 (R-II). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are given in Table 2.

Composition of the complexes : The composition of the complexes were determined by Job's method^{1,2} using equimolar solutions of reagents (2.63×10^{-4} M R-I and 5.00×10^{-4} M R-II) and metal ion. The composition was found to be 1 : 1 for both the complexes (Fig. 3). The compositions were verified by mole-ratio method (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2. Ringbom's plot.

Reagent	Molar absorptivity $l.mole^{-1}cm^{-1}$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu g Os^{6+}/cm$	log K	
			Leden's method	Harvey-Mannings method
I	8.3×10^3	0.028	4.62	4.71
II	6.5×10^3	0.029	4.00	4.52

Fig. 3. Job's plot.

$Os^{6+} = R-I = 2.63 \times 10^{-4} M$, $Os^{6+} = R-II = 5.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Effect of diverse ions : It was observed that 100 fold excess of Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Ir^{4+} , Ru^{3+} , Rh^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , citrate, tartrate, oxalate, EDTA, acetate, nitrate, sulphate and fluoride had no adverse effect on the determination of Os^{6+} by both the reagents. 20 fold (R-I) and 30 fold (R-II) excess of Ti^{4+} did not show any interference. Mo^{6+} , W^{6+} , V^{5+} , Pt^{4+} and Pd^{2+} interfered.

Fig. 4. Mole-ratio curve.

$O_3^{6+} = R-I = 1.58 \times 10^{-3} M$, $O_3^{6+} = R-II = 1.58 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Stability constants: The overall formation constants calculated from Harvey-Manning's¹³

method and Leden's¹⁴ method at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ are reported in Table 2.

References

1. E. B. SANDELL, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Analyt. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 342.
2. W. J. ALLAN and F. E. BEAMISH, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1952, **24**, 1608.
3. STEIGER, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1934, **16**, 193.
4. F. E. BEAMISH, *Talanta*, 1965, **12**, 801.
5. A. K. MAJUMDAR and J. G. SEN GUPTA, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1959, **26**, 532.
6. A. K. MAJUMDAR and S. K. BHOWAL, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1972, **62**, 223.
7. S. C. SHOME, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 603.
8. M. GUZMAN, D. PEREZ-BENDITO and F. PINO, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1976, **83**, 259.
9. G. BAIULESCU, C. LAZAR and C. CRISTESCU, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1961, **24**, 464.
10. H. D. PORTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 127.
11. A. RINGBOM, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1938/39, **115**, 332.
12. P. JOB, *Comp. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928; *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
13. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488; 1952, **74**, 4744.
14. I. LEDEN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1941, **160**, 188A.